

ANISOTROPIC COUPLING EFFECTS USED IN AN ALL-NEW SHAFT/HUB-JOINT FOR PRINTING APPLICATIONS MADE OF REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent lightweight construction permits an increasing in process quality and robustness by implementing modern technologies in printing press manufacture. Due to their strength/stiffness-to-weight ratio fibre-reinforced composites are suitable for printing applications. Beyond the classical lightweight approach the usage of material based anisotropic coupling effects of fibre-reinforced plastics is a very interesting technical solution for increasing the functional relationships between deformation and mechanical load of such structures made of multi-layered fibre-reinforced plastics. In this thesis an all-new shaft/hub-joint that uses these complex anisotropic coupling effects of fibre-reinforced composites, was developed and applied in a lightweight rapid clamping system for gravure package printing. Regarding the structural analysis, a theory of thick walled cylindrical shells was utilised and experimentally and numerical verified. Therefore, some basis fibre-reinforced shafts produced in filament winding were axial loaded and the load-depending maximum torque that could be transferred to a metallic hub was measured. The resulting deformation of the fibre-reinforced shafts was also analysed by using a greyscale correlation measuring system. Based on these results style guidelines for fibre-reinforced composite parts using these coupling effects were established and approached holistically by analysing the entire value chain. The developed fibre-reinforced rapid clamping system was released 2012 during the world's largest trade show for print media "Drupa" in Düsseldorf and evoked a positive customer response.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last decades a lot of industry sectors focus on lightweight construction for research and development. The increasing weight optimization of structures, parts and components lead to a saving of resources during the production and use phase. Especially the weight reduction of mobile applications allows to improve the energy efficiency and to reduce the emission of pollutants. Beside these classical concepts of lightweight construction the utilization of material immanent anisotropic coupling effects is an interesting solution for increasing the product benefits made out of fibre reinforced plastic (FRP). This coupling effect results from the direction depending stiffness of the unidirectional single layer and leads to a complex structural analysis of such anisotropic laminates. The focussed use of coupling effects in FRP needs an exact knowledge of the mechanical properties of the unidirectional single layer and the deformation state as well as detailed information of the strength behaviour of the composite. The calculation, design and production of FRP with anisotropic coupling effects is not considered to be part of the state of art and requires normally a complex optimisation of the fibre orientation in consideration of production-related restriction. On this account most of the published works to this topic focus basic research and the related products are not beyond a technical prototype.

A first example of a viable product with anisotropic coupling effects is a snowboard that was developed at the Institute of Structure Lightweight at the Technische Universität Chemnitz and is now distributed by silbaerg. This sporting-good uses a bending-torsion-coupling to increase and influence the handling characteristic. For the calculation of this snowboard robust and enlarged design strategies based on a numerical approach had been developed and were successful verified in lab and field experiments. These unusual coupling effects could be also used beside the sports industry. One example is machinery with its typical rotational symmetric parts like a shaft/hub-joint there, such material immanent anisotropic coupling effects could be used to create a simple and high-precision lightweight system for a fast change of printing cylinders in printing presses.

2 GRAVURE-PRINTING PRCESS AND CYLINDERS

Classic gravure printing applications consider of a gravure-printing cylinder (2) (see Figure 1) [1] made of metallic material due to gravure printing typical extreme linear loads at the print column and limited tolerances for the resulting bending deformation. During the printing process the whole gravure-printing cylinder is inked at an ink baht (1) and the surplus ink is wiped off through the doctor blade (3), so that only the defined amount of ink is filed in the cells. With a sufficient contact pressure between the gravure-printing cylinder and impression roller (5) the ink is transferred from the cells to the printing substrate by adhesive forces ([2], [3] and [1]).

Figure 1: Systematic overview of an inking unit of a gravure printing machine.

During a normal gravure-printing process the pressure between the booth cylinders has a line load of 20 N/mm and the maximum deformation requirement of 0.1 mm/m of the gravure-printing cylinder should not be exceeded because of potential register faults while printing more than one color in a line [4]. Due to this stiffness requirement classic gravure-printing cylinders are made of metal and have a small potential for lightweight construction that is determined by the wall thickness of the cylinder. A further weight reduction is possible if the deformation requirement is changed or if new lightweight concepts are developed. One of these new concepts is the so-called sleeve system, which consist of a thin metal cylinder with the printing gravure that is mechanical shrunk on a stiff metal support cylinder that meets the deformation requirements ([5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10] and [11]). This functional separation allows a material optimization of booth components and leads to a lighter gravure-printing system.

3 ELASTIC MATERIAL LAW FOR ANISOTROPIC MATERIALS AND MULTI-LAYER CYLINDRIC SHELLS

FRP with thermoset matrix are classified as brittle materials, which have a nearly linear elastic behavior up to fracture. Continuum mechanic explain these materials as anisotropic homogeneous objects and the mathematical description of the mechanical behavior of such objects is done by the generalized Hooke's law:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = S_{ijkl}\sigma_{kl} \quad (1)$$

Contrary to this assumption FRP with thermoplastic matrix are rate as pseudo-plastic or viscoelastic materials, which need a non-linear approach for an exact description of their mechanical behavior. These non-linear aspects must be taken into account if the results of this work should be transferred to an FPR anisotropic shaft/hub-joint with thermoplastic matrix [12]. The effect of temperature change on the structural deformation is not considered during this work because of constant room temperature during the printing process. Additional the FRP parts of the anisotropic shaft/hub-joint do not come into contact with ink during the printing process so that the structural effects of media concentration are also ignored.

The essential compliance matrix for the elastic material law S_{ijkl} is direction depending values which are often described as a material constant with a linear tensor fourth order. Due to symmetrical properties of the strain and stiffness tensor the compliance tensors of the generalized Hooke's law could be simplified:

$$S_{ijkl} = S_{ijlk} = S_{jikl} = S_{jilk} \quad (2)$$

By assumption of the existence of the density of distortion $U(e_{ij})$ as a function of the distortion of the hyper elastic material law [13] a further simplification could be done:

$$S_{ijkl} = S_{klij}. \quad (3)$$

Material Structure	S_{ij}, C_{ij}
Triclinical Anisotropy	
Hexagonal Anisotropy (Transversal Isotropy)	
Monoclinical Anisotropy	
Cubical Anisotropy (Isotropy)	
Rhombical Anisotropy (Orthotropic)	

$S_{ij}, C_{ij} \neq 0$
 $S_{ij} = S_{kl}, C_{ij} = C_{kl}$
 $S_{ij}, C_{ij} = 0$

★
 $S_{il} = 2(S_{11} - S_{12}),$

★
 $C_{il} = (C_{11} - C_{12})/2$

Figure 2: Variants of anisotropy and according relationships [13] and [14].

The amount of independent variables is reduced from 81 to 21 components by using (2) and (3). In the case of special symmetric aspects of the material some components of the compliance matrix take the value of zero and the amount of independent values is simultaneous reduced. In the case of isotropic materials only two independent components exist (see Figure 2).

The calculation of multi-layered cylindrical shells (see Figure 3, left) is based on the mechanical structural behavior of a unidirectional reinforced single layer with an orthotropic material behavior that is defined by a fiber adapted (1,2,3)-coordinate system. In case of a rotationally symmetric layout of the unidirectional single layers a cylindrical (r, φ, z) -coordinate system is used and a Polar Transformation of the constitutive equations is necessary. The necessary transformation equations are described in detail in KROLL [13]. Regarding the cylindrical (r, φ, z) -coordinate system the unidirectional single layer has a monoclinic material behavior and also simple loads lead to a complex three-dimensional stress and distortion state.

Figure 3: Lay-up of a multi-layer shell with its coordinate system (left) and rotational symmetric loads in cylindrical coordinate system (right) [13] and [14].

For calculation a multi-layer cylindrical shell the FRP is divided in single layer with an arbitrary fiber orientation. Whereby, production-based interactions of the single layer like the crossing of the fibers during the cross winding process is not considered and the mechanical basic equations of the anisotropic cylindrical objects are used. According to the classical lamina theory these equations are transferred to the structural law of the cylindrical multi-layer composite by using transition conditions. Thereby a complete adhesion of the single layers among each other is assumed. According to the load case further transition and boundary conditions should be considered.

The basic equations of the mechanic of anisotropic objects in a cylindrical coordinate system are defined for the following loads by KROLL [13]:

- Axial tension F_z and pressure F_D ,
- Torsion M_t
- Internal p_i and external p_a pressure
- Centrifugal force w and
- Radial heat transfer ΔT .

For such rotationally symmetric loads the stress-deformation behavior of an FRP-shaft is adjustable by the orientation angel of the fibers. Thus, the anisotropic material potential could be used optimal.

Regarding the calculation of such an FRP-shaft there are several assumptions like, force transmission areas, notches and sections do not exist as well as any inhomogeneity. Therefore, no shear stress in the inner and outer shell surface τ_{rz} and $\tau_{r\phi}$ exists [13]:

$$\tau_{rz} = \tau_{r\phi} = 0. \quad (4)$$

Thus, for a cylindrical coordinate system the following equilibrium condition exists:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\phi}{r} + F_r = 0, \quad (5)$$

with F_r as a volume force in the direction of that coordinate axis that is not considered here.

With assumption of small deformations and a derivative of deformation toward one, the deformations and distortions could be described according to the kinematical equation 6 – 11 [13] and [14]:

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \quad (6) \rightarrow \quad \varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_r(r) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_\varphi = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{u}{r} \quad (7) \rightarrow \quad 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\varepsilon_z = \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \quad (8) \rightarrow \quad \varepsilon_z = \varepsilon_z(z) = \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_{\varphi z} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \varphi} \quad (9) \rightarrow \quad \tau_{\varphi z} = \tau_{\varphi z}(r) = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \quad (15)$$

$$\tau_{rz} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \quad (10) \rightarrow \quad 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\tau_{r\varphi} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} - \frac{v}{r} \quad (11) \rightarrow \quad 0 \quad (17)$$

with u, v, w as the deformations in r, φ, z direction.

This partial differential equation for the deformation components u, v, w are over determined. Thus, the distortion components of the according compatibility condition [13] are not independent. Due to the rotational symmetric loads the strains and distortions are dependent on r and the kinematic equations are simplified to 12 – 17.

Regarding wounded FRP layers with an arbitrary fibre orientation, the constitutive equation for monoclinic anisotropy after a rotational transformation about the 1-axis is [13] and [14]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_\varphi \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{\varphi z} \\ \gamma_{rz} \\ \gamma_{r\varphi} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ & & S_{33} & S_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & S_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & sym. & & & S_{55} & S_{56} \\ & & & & & S_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\varphi \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{\varphi z} \\ \tau_{rz} \\ \tau_{r\varphi} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

With $S_{ij} = C_{ij}^{-1}$ and $(i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ as compliance component and equation 18 the coupling C_{55}, C_{56}, C_{66} out of the single layer plane does not exist:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\varphi \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{\varphi z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & C_{34} \\ C_{14} & C_{24} & C_{34} & C_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_\varphi \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{\varphi z} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

After entering the constitutive equation 18, and the kinematic equation 10 and 11 with consideration of 12 – 17 the deformation could be described as [13]:

$$u = u(r) \quad (20)$$

$$v = K_d \cdot r \cdot z \quad (21)$$

$$w = K_c \cdot z \quad (22)$$

with the constants K_c describing the strain in axial direction and K_d describing the twisting of the FRP-shaft that are depending of coupling effects of the anisotropic FRP-shaft. Using the equilibrium condition (22), as well as the cinematic relations (12) – (17), (4) and (20) – (22) leads to a usually inhomogeneous differential equation of 2nd order:

$$C_{11}r^2 \frac{d^2u}{dr^2} + C_{11}r \frac{du}{dr} - C_{22}u = -(C_{13} - C_{23})K_c r - (2C_{14} - C_{24})K_d r^2. \quad (23)$$

that is solved in KROLL [13].

4 ALL-NEW SHAFT/HUB-JOINT

Based on the theoretical fundamentals an anisotropic shaft/hub-joint for the focused gravure printing process could be developed that use an FRP-shaft with a defined radial deformation according to a given axial load to design a frictional connection between the FRP-shaft and a metallic hub. Through the specific exploitation of the anisotropic coupling effects of the FRP the new anisotropic shaft/hub-joint could be significantly improved compared to classic ones with metal shaft and hub. Two of the relevant stress and strain concepts that are working with an axial tensile and pressure load are shown in Figure 3. Beside these concepts there are also anisotropic shaft/hub-joints that operate with a torsion load, internal positive and negative pressure as well as temperature loads [14].

No.	Load Concept	Before Joining	While Joining	After Joining
1	Axial Tensile Load			
2	Axial Pressure Load			

Figure 4: Stress and strain concepts of selected anisotropic shaft/hub-joint [14].

The 1st concept bases on an axial tensile load on the FRP-shaft. Due to the anisotropic coupling of F_z and ϵ_r the shaft diameter is reduced by the force F_z . The shaft/hub-joint for this concept is designed with a loose fit in the loaded case (left picture) and the hub could be placed easily on the anisotropic FRP-shaft during the fusion process (picture in the middle). Without the tensile load the anisotropic FRP-shaft returns to his un-deformed diameter and the loose fit change into a press fit. According to the defined oversize of the unloaded shaft different torque values could be transmitted form the FRP-shaft to the hub [14].

Focusing an axial pressure load the operation principle is just the other way around. The joining process takes place in the unloaded state with a loose fit between the both components (left and middle picture). After loading the anisotropic FPR-shaft with an axial pressure (right picture) the diameter of the shaft enlarged and a press fit between the booth components results. This leads to an additional multi-axial stress state inside the FRP-shaft during the joined status that could increase the load capacity due to the inner material friction [14].

Based on the theoretical aspects of the deformation of a loaded FRP-shaft a solution approach for calculation the transmissible torque is given. Therefore, the metallic hub is assumed to be rigid and non-deformable. Thus, the joining diameter of the FRP-shaft D_F is equal to the inner diameter of the hub D_{Ai} :

$$D_F = D_{Ai} \quad (24)$$

Furthermore both parts have the same length and the axial displacement of the FRP-shaft due to the axial load is ignored and it is also assumed that the surfaces of the joining components touch each other in a complete and ideal way. In addition, a linear elastic material behavior is valid so that the Hooke's law could be used for calculating the stress and strain states. Regarding case number two, an anisotropic shaft/hub-joint that works with a pressure load, both components have a loose fit for the unloaded state (see Figure 5 left side) with:

$$D_{Ai} < D_F \quad (25)$$

Figure 5: Anisotropic shaft/hub-joint (No. 2) unloaded (left), loaded (right) [14].

While loading the FRP-shaft with an axial pressure F_z the diameter increases due to the anisotropic coupling to a value D_{Ia} with a penetration of both components:

$$D_{Ia} + 2u(r) > D_F \quad (26)$$

In the second step of the calculation process the resulting diameter of the FPR-shaft is transferred to an unloaded cylinder (#) with:

$$D_{Ia}^\# = D_{Ia} + 2u(r) \quad (27)$$

Figure 6: Unloaded cylinder (#) of an anisotropic shaft/hub-joint (No. 2) unloaded (left), loaded with $p_a(D_{Ia}^\#=D_F)$ (right) [14].

Then, the cylinder (#) is loaded with an external pressure p_a until the diameter is equal to the joining diameter:

$$D_{Ia}^\# - 2u(r) = D_F. \quad (28)$$

With

$$p_a(D_{Ia}^\#=D_F) = p_r \quad (29)$$

and

$$T = \frac{\pi}{2} D_F^2 l_P \mu_u \frac{p_r}{S_R} \quad (30)$$

the transmittable torque could be calculated.

For an anisotropic FRP-shaft/hub-joint with an exemplary hub diameter of 102.05 mm, an axial load of -20 kN and four exemplary material combinations (see Table 1) with an two layer-layup with $\pm\alpha$ and a layer thickness of 0.5 mm a maximum transmittable torque of 250 Nm could be calculated that is also shown in Figure 7.

Material	φ	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ϑ_{12}	ϑ_{13}	ϑ_{23}	E_3	G_{23}	G_{13}
T300/EP	0.60	138	11	5.5	0.28	0.28	0.66	11	2.1	5.5
E/EP	0.62	53.5	17.7	5.4	0.28	0.28	0.67	17.7	1.9	5.4
UHM1/EP	0.60	518	53.4	5.5	0.32	0.32	0.65	53.4	1.8	5.5
UHM2/EP	0.60	381	42.4	2.9	0.35	0.35	0.65	42.4	1.8	2.9

Table 1: Mechanical properties of selected FRP.

Figure 7: Calculated transmittable torque of an anisotropic shaft/hub-joint with balanced angle $\pm\alpha$ with an axial load of -20 kN

Independently of the material combination the maximum value occurs for an orientation angel $\alpha = 45^\circ$ and the material combination UHM2/EP3.

In case of shafts with a greater length then the hub, there are additional radial deformation effects in the areas that are not covered by the hub because the rigid hub does not limit the coupling related deformation in these areas. Hence, it is necessary do differ in areas with and without overlapping for calculating the transmittable torque of such anisotropic FRP-shaft/hub-joints. In the areas without overlapping the axial load leads to a deformation, also in the joint state that is greater than the joining diameter:

$$D_{Ia} + 2u > D_F \quad (31)$$

The calculation of the mechanical behavior in the areas between the zones with the defined deformation status is very complex due to additional stress and strain interactions. Hence, the resulting deformation of such anisotropic FRP-shaft/hub-joints should be done by FE-analysis like it is shown in [14] and [15].

6 SERIAL APPLICATION

Based on the analytical analysis that was shown in this work, a complex FE-analysis ([14] and [15]) and comprehensive experimental studies [15] an all-new FRP gravure printing system was developed and published at the worldwide biggest trade show for printing dices (Drupa) in 2012 [16]. The worldwide first printing device using anisotropic coupling effects of FRP consists of a stiff support cylinder made of anisotropic FRP (1) (see Figure 8), an adapter helix (2) and a thickness variable sleeve (3) [17].

Figure 8: Serial shaft/hub-joint for gravure printing.

The axial length of the components varies according to the customer requirements as well as the geometry of the adapters at the faces of the anisotropic FRP shaft. The operating system of the axial pressure load (No. 2) is implemented by an integrated clamping system based on a thread rod. The radial deformation of the anisotropic FRP shaft is controlled by a torque wrench that fits in one of the metal adapter and the mounting process of a sleeve needs only a few seconds.

A new hybrid lightweight gravure printing systems could be developed by using this all-new an innovative approach of an anisotropic FRP-shaft/hub-joint. The advantages of the new system are the fast and easy mounting process of the sleeves as well as cost and weight benefits according to classic system made of metal. The explicit shorten mounting process lead to reduced set-up times during the printing process and allow an evident improvement of the process efficiency.

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